

Efficacy of Anantmool as Medhya Dravya

Dr. D. V. Kulkarni¹, Dr. Renuka S. Pawar², Dr. Ruchita R. Kudale^{3*}

¹Head of Dept., Dravyaguna Dept., Government Ayurvedic College, Osmanabad

^{2,3}P.G.Scholar, Dravyaguna Dept., Government Ayurvedic College, Osmanabad

*Email of Corresponding Author: ³renuka.pawar2014@gmail.com

Abstract—In Ayurveda, term 'Medhya' is described in a broad way. Medhya comprises of all three mental faculties -Dhee, Dhriti and Smriti and these are interrelated with each other. Memory is a combination of Power of grasping (Grahan), Retention (Dharan) and Recollection (Smaran). Neurologic and psychiatric disorders are generally associated with loss of memory. Psychiatric disorders have become a major public health problem today. Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease are associated with impaired neurological functions. Acharya Sushruta has described Anantmool churna with madhu and ghruta for Lehan in children. Acharya kashyapa has mentioned that 'Lehan' has medha vardhak property in lehan adhyaya. Hemidesmus indicus R. Br. commonly known as "Anantmool" in Marathi, "Sariva" in Sanskrit and Indian sarsaparilla in English. It is a most useful plant in the Indian system of medicine. Sariva is in possession of Madhur- Tikta rasa, Madhur Vipaka and Sheet Virya. Regular use of Madhur rasa from birth promotes the growth of all the dhatu and helps in achieving goodness and clearness in sense organs. Anantmool can act as a good brain tonic. It can be used in children with psychiatric disorders. The present study assesses the potential of an ayurvedic rasayana drug 'Hemidesmus indicus R. Br.' roots as a memory enhancer. Anantmool churna is easily available throughout India and being cost effective, it can be affordable to people. This review shows the efficacy of Anantmool as Medhya dravya.

Keywords— Anantmool, Medhya, Lehan.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda represents an ancient system of traditional medicine in India which is about 5000 years old. Psychological disorders are seen in any age group and has become common problem of today's life style. Depression, anxiety disorders, hereditary, stress, fast food, dementia etc. are commonly seen In children; Psychological disorders have become quite common serving lifelong impact on his or her family^[1].

Mental illness is associated with abnormal level of neurotransmitters like serotonin or dopamine in the brain, decrease in the size of some areas of brain, as well as increased activity in other areas of the brain. It can be observed in other disorders like attention deficit hyperactivity, depression and anxiety^[1].

In old age patients, neurodegenerative changes are seen associated with Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease^[2] In Ayurveda, *Manas roga samprapti* can be described as-*Vata, pitta* and *Kapha Prakopa* (Tridosha Prakopa), *chinta, bhaya, shoka, krodha* causing *sandnyavah strotas avarodha*. This results into *indriya vikruti* which is responsible for *smrutinash*^[3].

Ayurveda has described various kinds of mental disorders as follows^[4]-

1. *Unmada* (Insanity)
2. *Apasmara* (Epilepsy)
3. *Atattvaabhinivesha* (Obsessive Disorders)
4. *Bhaya* (fear)
5. *Harsha* (Excitation)
6. *Shoka* (Grief)
7. *Udvega* (Anxiety)
8. *Avasada* (Depression)

In Ayurveda; *Vata, pitta* and *Kapha doshas* are responsible for regulation of all human body function. *Vata* is responsible for association of ideas, *Pitta* is responsible for understanding

and attaining knowledge and *Kapha* is responsible for providing stability needed for retention of memory^[5].

Anantmool (*Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br.) is an important medicinal plant of tropical and subtropical India. The name Hemidesmus derived from Latin word Hemidesmos which means half bond. Word indicus stands for of India. *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br. belongs to family *Asclepiadaceae* which is derived from word Asklepios means God of medicine.^[6] *Anantmool* is a Sanskrit name of *Sariva* which means 'endless root'^[7].

Aim

To analyse *Medhya* effect of *Anantmool churna*.

Objectives

- To study ayurvedic aspect of *Anantmool* as a *Medhya dravya*.
- To study efficacy, mode of action and modern research on *Anantmool*.

II. METHODOLOGY

Ayurvedic Aspect:

- Acharya Sushruta in *Sharirsthana* has described that *Anantmool churna* along with *Madhu* and *Ghruta* for *Lehan* in children after *Jatkarma paricharya*.^[8]
- Acharya kashyapa has mentioned that *Lehan* has *medha vardhak* property in *lehan adhyaya* of *Sutrasthana*.^[9]
- Acharya Vagbhata has described that 1st day after birth, *Anantmool churna* with *madhu* and *ghruta* for *Lehan* in children.^[10]
- Acharya Vagbhata in *Utartantra balopcharniya adhyaya* has described that *Brahmi, Vacha* and *Sariva Siddha Ghruta* for *medha and smriti vardhak* in children.^[11]
- Acharya Charaka has mentioned *kalyanaka, Mahakalyanaka ghruta* in *Manas roga chikitsa* (*Unmad chikitsa*) which contains *Anantmool*.^[12]

Synonyms^[13]

Krushna Sariva – Sariva, shyama, gopee, gopvadh.
Shweta Sariva – Dhavla, Sariva, gopa, gopkanya,
krushodhari, sfota, shyama, gopavalali, lata, aasfota,
Chandana.

Vernacular Names^[12]

Hindi- *Magrabu, salsa, kapooree, Anantmool.*
Marathi- *Anantmool, Upalsari.*
English – *Indian Sarsaparilla.*
Bengal – *Anantmool.*
Gujrat – *Upalsari, kapooree, kunder, kagadiyo.*
Telugu – *Palsugandhi*
Tamil – *Nannari.*

Habitat^[13]

Anantmool is a soft, tender, winding shrub which is commonly found in most parts of India.

It is commonly available in Bengal, Bombay and Himalaya.

Raspanchka of *Anantmool* –

Rasa- Madhur, Tikta
Guna- Guru, Snigdha
Virya- Shita
Vipaka- Madhur
Doshakarma - Tridoshashamak

Modern aspect

Taxonomical classification^[14]

Botanical name- *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br
Kingdom – Plantae
Subkingdom – Angiosperms
Order – Gentianales
Family – Apocynaceae
Genus – *Hemidesmus*
Species – *H. indicus*

Morphology

Anantmool is climber found throughout India. Leaves are 2.5 inches long and alternatively arranged in pair. Superior part is oval in shape and it is very soft. Stem is cylindrical with nodes. Woody roots are underground part and are aromatic. Flower is cluster yellow and greenish purple in colour. Fruits are 2-4 inch long. Seeds are black in colour, flattened with silvery white coma^[15]. Leaves and roots have medicinal properties.

Chemical composition^[13]

It contains essential oil, Starch, Coumarin, Tannic acid, Triterpenoid saponins, Hemidesmin

III. DISCUSSION

What is *Medhya Rasayana*

The word '*Medhya rasayana*' have been derived from the Sanskrit word '*Medhya*' meaning intellect and *rasayana* meaning 'rejuvenation'. The medicinal plant in *Ayurveda* classified as brain tonic or rejuvenators^[16]. Neurological disorders generally associated with declining mental function,

loss of memory, cognitive anabolise etc. *Medhya rasayana dravya* having antioxidant, anti-stress action induces sleep and increases circulation into the CNS system. Hence help to improve *Medhya* function.

Medhya rasayana in neuroprotective action

Medhya rasayana dravya plays important role in the treatment of Psychological disorders.

On the basis of experimental and clinical research, it is known that varying degree of psychotropic action are known to have antidepressant, sedative and tranquilizing action. *Medhya dravya* are promoting the function of *Buddhi* and *Manas* by correcting disturbances of *Rajas* and *Tamas bhava*^[17]. It helps mental patient to get relief from stress, anxiety and depression. Regeneration of tissue in conditions like Alzheimer and Parkinson's disease may be possible with use of *Ayurvedic Medhya rasayana Dravyas*^[15].

Anantmool churna- Medhya action

Hemidesmus indicus R.Br. (*Sariva*) is in possession of *Madhur- tikta rasa, Madhur Vipaka, Sheet Virya* and *Guru, Snigdha Gunas*.

Madhur rasa is *Shadindriya prasadak, kaphavardhak* and nourishes all *dhatu*s. *Indriya vikruti* present in *manas roga* can be cured by *Madhur rasa*. *Tikta rasa* promotes *pitta* and enhances "*Grahan karma*" (power of grasping). *Sheet Virya* and *Madhur Vipaka* also promotes *Tarpaka Kapha* and enhances "*Dharan karma*" (retention)^[18]. *Tridoshaprakopa* present in *Manas rogas* can be treated with *Anantmool* as it is having *Tridoshashamak* activity.

Researchers have proved that *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. is having anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. Anti-inflammatory action protects the brain from inflammatory lesions caused by any trauma and helps to enhance memory. Anti-oxidant action reduces brain damage and protects brain cells. These activities of *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. enhances memory.^[19]

Previous research work

- Shete R V et al (2010) studied the effect of *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. root ethanolic extract (3,10 and 30 mg / kg p.o.) on mice and found that HI extract significantly improves learning capacity and memory at all doses in mice^[20].
- D. Sivaraman et al (2012) studied the effect of *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. root methanol extract on (200 and 400 mg / kg p.o.) cerebral ischemia in Sprague-Dawley rats and observed that *Hemidesmus indicus* R.Br. root methanol extract significantly increase the anti-oxidant enzymes in brain and neurological status can be improved^[21].

IV. CONCLUSION

In modern medicine; drugs used for treatment of psychological disorders have many side effects. *Ayurveda* has described few herbs as *medhya dravya*. It is known that *medhya dravya* can act on *sharir* and *manas bhava*. *Anantmool* improves *Grahan karma* (power of grasping) and

Dharan karma (retention). Modern researchers have proved anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant action of *Anantmoool* and also observed its memory enhancing activity. It is easily available, affordable, non-controversial and easily identified as compare to other *medhya dravyas* for masses. This may give a helping hand to patients of psychological disorders.

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